

SHORT NOTES

Slow-coagulation Equation of Titanium Oxide Sol

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Though Smoluchowski's equation¹ for the rate of coagulation was shown to hold good for rapid coagulation, it was found to be inadequate for the slow rate even with its modified form. To account for the observed facts, the equation, as modified by Ghosh², stands as

$$n_t = n_0 \frac{(1 + \alpha t)}{(1 + \beta t)}$$

It was amply verified from the ultramicroscopic data of several authors^{3,4}. The corresponding spectrophotometric equation

$$D_t = D_i \frac{(1+bt)}{(1+at)}$$

was also verified². This spectrophotometric equation, instead of writing in terms of galvanometer deflections, can also be expressed as

$$I_t = I_i \frac{(1 + bt)}{(1 + at)}$$

where I_i and I_t are the percentage transmissions of the sol-electrolyte system at $t=0$ and at any other time t , a and b being constants.

This equation was shown^{2,5} to hold good for the slow coagulation of ThO_2 and CeO_2 sols. The object of this note is to lend further support to the above equation, using our data on slow coagulation of TiO_2 sol.

Preparation of the Colloid.—Following Majumdar's method⁶, the sol was prepared by hydrolysis of TiCl_4 at a low temperature, followed by dialysis and ageing for a suitable period. The stable positively charged sol, almost colorless, had a concentration of 0.12%, pH 5.1, and sp. conductance at $25^\circ = 1.23 \times 10^{-4}$ mho. cm^{-1} . The method of studying coagulation is described elsewhere⁴. Transmittance was measured with the help of a Beckman DU spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched cells at $\lambda=546\text{m}\mu$; the temperature was maintain-

1. *Physikal. Z.*, 1916, 17, 657; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1917, 92, 129.
2. Ghosh? this *Journal*, 1959, 35, 671 et seq.
3. Ghosh and Gangopadhyay, *ibid.*, 1959, 36, 811.
4. Ghosh and Bandyopadhyay, *ibid.*, 1962, 39, 309.
5. Bandyopadhyay, *ibid.*, 1962, 39, 453.
6. *ibid.*, 1929, 6, 357.

ed at 25°. Only univalent coagulating ions were used; polyvalent counter ions could not be used for reasons already mentioned in the case of ThO_2 sol.

Assuming suitable values for a and b , a theoretical curve for each electrolyte concentration was constructed by a method previously described²⁻³. From a study of such curves, shown in Fig. 1, it appears that the experimental points satisfactorily fit in the theoretical curve.

FIG. 1 t (mins.)

TABLE I

Values of	a	and	b	corresponding to	C_{KCl}	for curve
	6.6×10^{-2}		2.5×10^{-2}	21mM/litre		1
	2.0×10^{-2}		9.0×10^{-3}	15		2
	2.4×10^{-3}		2.47×10^{-4}	10		3
	3.5×10^{-3}		3.15×10^{-3}	8		4

Mehta and Joseph⁷ studied the slow coagulation kinetics of TiO_2 sol. They obtained prominent S-shaped curves which the present author failed to notice with the well-purified sol. The appearance of S-shape in a coagulation curve was shown⁴ to be connected with the presence of sufficient amount of co-ions, such as, in sols dialysed for a short period. Suitable explanation for the constants a and b is still lacking.

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